

D8.2 Detailed version of the communication and dissemination plan

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Summary			
<p>MiniStor's communication and dissemination strategy evolved significantly in response to internal and external challenges. In consequence, this document is structured to guide the reader through this changes, from strategic planning to the final outcomes. It features the updates on strategy, implementation activities and materials produced, with detailed although comprehensive performance metrics. D8.2 offers insights into how a complex H2020 Research and Innovation Action adapted throughout 68 months, engaged the public using refined techniques, and delivered lasting impact beyond project lifetime.</p> <p>MiniStor's communication and dissemination efforts were mostly successful and provided value in line with expectations, demonstrating adaptability, strategic alignment, and strong links with EU-level initiatives. The project met or exceeded most KPIs, including website traffic, video views, and outreach, though it fell slightly short in social media growth and scientific publications due to timeline constraints. The Final Conference showcased the project's achievements and policy relevance. Overall, Work Package 8 achieved the desired impact on the general public and end-users of sustainable thermal energy storage technologies, while offering valuable insights for future EU-funded initiatives.</p>			
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Executive summary

Deliverable D8.2 is the final update of the communication and dissemination plan for the MiniStor project. The document reflects the implementation of the strategy laid out in Deliverable D8.1 and evaluates its effectiveness through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), stakeholder engagement, and outreach activities.

Work Package 8 (WP8) focused on three main goals: defining and executing a communication strategy, promoting project acceptance through standardization and policy engagement, and linking MiniStor with existing networks to foster knowledge transfer. The communication plan was structured (see section 4.1.2 of D8.1) into five phases, from initial awareness to final results dissemination. A strategic framework was developed early in the project, including branding guidelines, a Book of Style, and templates to ensure visual consistency.

The strategy was disrupted by a temporary project suspension in 2022, requiring WP8 to realign its priorities. Despite this, the consortium increased collaboration through biweekly technical meetings and adapted dissemination efforts to focus on technical impact and industry networking. The introduction of new partners and feedback from reviewers further shaped the communication approach.

MiniStor utilized a variety of channels, including a dedicated website, social media (LinkedIn and X/Twitter), newsletters, press releases, promotional videos, and the Zenodo repository. The website, launched in Month 6, became the central hub for project updates and public deliverables, achieving over 3,700 monthly visitors in its final year. Social media engagement varied, with LinkedIn surpassing its follower target while X/Twitter fell short due to platform instability due to constant changes to its algorithm and user base.

WP8 produced brochures, flyers, infographics, and rollups to support public engagement. Three newsletters and seven press releases were distributed, and four promotional videos were created, exceeding the KPI of 1,000 views. The Zenodo repository ensured long-term access to scientific outputs, with 258 downloads and 243 visualizations.

Three policy briefs were developed addressing thermal storage technologies, PVT development, and ammonia usage in residential settings. These were distributed during the Final Conference and served as key tools for engaging policymakers. Scientific dissemination included six peer-reviewed publications, with more expected post-project due to the complexity of the integrated technologies.

MiniStor participated in 27 international and 8 national events, reaching nearly 500,000 individuals across stakeholders, industry, academia, and the general public. The Final Conference, held during EU Sustainable Energy Week 2025, showcased project results and policy recommendations, attracting 164 attendees and 97 online participants.

The MiniStor project provided the expected value to the dissemination and communication activities through strategic planning, successful participation in key EU-level events and networks, and delivery of materials such as policy briefs and promotional videos. However, it faced drawbacks including delays due to project suspension, underperformance in some KPIs like social media reach and scientific publications, and challenges in maintaining consistent visibility across all channels.

Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Explanation
D	Deliverable
EeB PPP	Energy Efficient Buildings Public Private Partnership (succeeded by the ECTP)
EC	European Commission
ECTP	European Construction Technology Platform
EU	European Union
EUSEW	European Sustainable Energy Week event
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEMS	Home Energy Management System
H2020	Horizon 2020 Programme
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of the Project Results
PCM	Phase-Change Materials
PVT	Photovoltaic Thermal
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
TMC	Thermochemical Material
TRL	Technological Readiness Level
UNE	Spanish Association for Standardization

Introduction

This document is the final update of the communication and dissemination plan for project MiniStor.

In the work plan for MiniStor, Work Package 8 addressed three main objectives:

- To define and implement the communication and dissemination strategy
- To promote project acceptance through standardization and relevant policy-influencing bodies highlighting innovation potential of the system
- To link MiniStor with existing networks, projects and initiatives to promote an effective and efficient transfer of knowledge and to find common solutions to challenges posed by current regulations that are based on conventional technologies

Within the first of the objectives, Task 8.1 ran from the start of the project until Month 68 to set-up the communication and dissemination system of the project, by defining clear objectives and providing guidelines for all partners with a strategic plan, branding models, and communication channels centred around the project website. Although led by FEUGA, all partners were consulted and took part in the realisation of the communication and dissemination strategy.

A Book of Style was also made available alongside the first version of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy (D8.1) at M3 addressing the MiniStor visual identity (i.e. logo, styles, and templates) and the rules to be followed by all project partners in order to maintain an efficient and homogenous sense of brand.

Submitted in December 2020, the sixth version of Deliverable D8.1 set the consensual strategy to reach the determined target audiences, including dedicated objectives and indicators to evaluate the performance, key messages, communication products (e.g. media campaigns, infographics, policy briefs), channels, timing and responsibilities among the partners; as well as foreseen publications on the basis of the main findings of MiniStor.

As a living document, D8.1 established the rationale behind WP8 actions throughout the project lifetime. Therefore, the subsequent D8.2 aims to reflect how the decisions were made in alignment with the strategy as it was implemented. It is only logical that a document submitted in the Month 13 out of 68 had to be modified, so an effort is made in the present report (D8.2) to acknowledge the context and realities of MiniStor that stem from its results, the input of reviewers and the liaisons needed to accomplish the objectives set for WP8 alongside SGS, ÉMI and R2M, responsible for major contributions to these activities.

In short, Deliverable 8.2 is not a companion of the strategy and guidelines, but an update on the actual implementation. It reflects the decision-making process and the outcomes of the actions taken throughout the project to ensure that Key Performance Indicators are fulfilled and that MiniStor's impacts continue beyond the period covered by the Grant funding.

Structure

The structure of Deliverable D8.2 is organized to reflect both strategic planning and implementation outcomes. It begins by outlining the objectives of Work Package 8 (WP8 onwards) and the rationale behind the communication and dissemination strategy. This is followed by a detailed explanation of the original plan laid out in Deliverable D8.1, including visual identity guidelines, communication phases, and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

The core of the document is structured around thematic sections that correspond to specific tasks and milestones within WP8. These include communication and dissemination actions, such as the website, social media, newsletters, press releases, videos, and Zenodo repository; the link to the standardization efforts and the clustering with other projects and the participation in events; and a list of policy briefs and scientific publications.

Each section provides both quantitative and qualitative analysis of the outcomes, supported by tables, figures, and excerpts from materials produced. D8.2 also includes a breakdown of the achieved communication and dissemination KPIs.

Finally, the document concludes with a reflective analysis of the successes and challenges encountered, emphasizing the adaptability of the strategy in response to disruptions such as the 2022 project suspension. It highlights the project's impact on policy, industry, and public awareness, and offers insights for future EU-funded initiatives. This structured approach ensures clarity, accountability, and a comprehensive overview of MiniStor's communication and dissemination efforts.

WP8 into context

The main objectives of this communication and dissemination plan were:

- Organize and guarantee an effective communication of the project messages, results and activities at a local, national and EU level.
- Identify appropriate target groups to address the communication and dissemination messages together with the tools, products, timing and channels to do so effectively.
- Implement a recognizable visual identity of the MiniStor project together with guidelines to do so correctly.
- Present the communication and dissemination KPIs previously agreed by the MiniStor consortium, useful and needed to measure the effectiveness of those quantifiable activities.
- Illustrate how the project will cooperate and interact in the residential energy efficiency sector ensuring a broad impact of the project and the prevalence of its results beyond project time.
- Update the communication and dissemination plan as needed to adapt to the circumstances that may arise during the development of the project.

The dissemination and communication strategy laid out in D8.1 initially envisioned five phases with the following timeline:

- initial awareness phase (M1-M14)
- strategic dissemination phase (M14-M26)
- mid-project results-oriented dissemination (M26-M30)
- second strategic dissemination phase (M30-M42)
- results dissemination phase (M42-M54)

D8.1 included, apart from the communication and dissemination plan, key communication and dissemination materials, templates and report mechanisms that have been already made available to consortium partners, in order to provide a consistent visual identity and a strong strategic

approach when it comes to executing communication and dissemination activities, as well as reporting them correctly.

Updates on the strategy up to final 6-months of the project

The strategy for the onset of the project was made available in M3 in the form of the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D8.1), with clear objectives and providing guidelines through two documents: Communication Guidelines with a strategic plan, and Social Media Guidelines.

To evaluate effectively the performance of this strategy, Communication and Dissemination KPIs were agreed upon by all members of the consortium and revised at each General Assembly. The strategy's performance is monitored through an online dissemination tracker, created for partners to enter their activities and dissemination achievements.

Halfway through the second year of the project, Work Package 8 activities were on track with the lines traced in Deliverable 8.1 (M13). Albeit a first version of the communication and dissemination plan, for it was created as a living document, the agreement and monitoring on the key performance indicators ensured that the actions were on track with the expected technical advances.

Accordingly, the third year started without alterations to the original planification, accomplishing regularly animated channels and networks that benefited from the partners' already existing platforms. It was a period of stabilisation for communication activities after the easing of most of the pandemic-related restrictions, and of first contacts for later dissemination efforts.

Shortly after, MiniStor's communication and dissemination system was temporarily disrupted by the temporary project suspension (January 2022) and subsequent amendment process. Hence, some arrangements were made to reconcile the different paces and priorities from the rest of the consortium. More precisely, WP8 was discontinued and had to be realigned after the suspension in a context of reduced consortium meetings.

As a supplementary measure, FEUGA was given access to biweekly technical meetings organised around WP6, getting first hand notice on dissemination opportunities. This continued throughout the project to great avail, producing an uptick in internal communication that allowed for better coordination, reducing WP8 meetings to the essential, and more in line with WP7 degree of access to technical developments, and thus avoiding duplication of requests.

During the temporary suspension, WP8 called a communication and dissemination meeting with task and work package leaders; gathering additional support from the coordination and the technical partners, two priorities were ultimately defined for M36: linking with similar initiatives within the heating and cooling technologies, and demonstrating the novel solutions proposed for the pilot and the sites. By achieving said dissemination objectives, MiniStor became ready and positioned to maximise outputs in this new stage which, crucially, saw the introduction of new partners.

For instance, the preliminary results from Task 8.3 were compiled within Deliverable 8.4 in June 2022. The document authored by SGS and ÉMI, and reviewed by CERTH and FEUGA, included the contacts made with relevant associations that represent energy storage, plus the introduction of the Product Audit Programme (PAP), which was later provided as a validated opinion. These elements helped establishing a dialogue with the standardisation bodies by showing the challenges and advances that could be achieved.

By contrast, the communication implementation suffered deviations that needed from maximising coordination efforts towards the end of the project. Actions not bind to specific initiatives and dates were put on hold, and the project could not be addressed as a whole until the eventual entry of the new partners. Focusing on technical impact and industry networking meant that communication campaigns, press releases and newsletters were postponed. However, the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) stayed the same, save for the 3 policy briefs to be produced as agreed in the first Review Meeting.

Following the stabilisation effort in response to the project suspension and amendment process, WP8 realigned priorities again: linking with relevant initiatives plus the end-user focus. This is shown more clearly after the project Review in April 2023, halfway through the timespan, when the recommendations from the reviewers were addressed and gradually implemented. Just as important was the incorporation of the new consortium members into the WP6 meetings routine, finally bringing together all the parts needed for a coherent promotion of the project activities.

By then, already on the dissemination phase of the strategy, progress had started in three policy groups, while the planning and execution of the communication activities became one with that of the Final Conference. It was to mobilise the highest C&D budget yet to showcase combination of policy insights and research results; in contrast to the mid-term event, this was set to be an in-person occasion. Besides, two newsletters and two press releases would accompany the Final Conference as the final promotional video was rolled out.

The first proposal was consulted and set for October 2024 alongside the Cluster 5 Info Days in Brussels co-organised by GREENET; more time was needed to complete the measurement of the units in the demosites, so the Final Conference was held in 2025 and merged with the EU Sustainable Energy Week campaign (more on this on the Events section), and Communication and Dissemination activities again suffered a blow due to the need to stretch Person Months until the end of the third extension.

With its transversal responsibility, Work Package 8 remained active for the duration of the project, save for the suspension period. Then again, the Key Performance Indicators were calculated for 54 months; sustaining the networks and joint initiatives, the online presence and the support of the dissemination actions for 68 months came at the cost of some figures not reaching the threshold, mainly due to the irregularity and the calendar changes that alter planning and compromises, although without major deviations, imbalances or quality decay. Overall, the value delivered was in line with expectations and the realities of a Research and Innovation Action.

Communication and Dissemination actions

1.1. Web performance

As planned, the project website [www.ministor.eu] was developed by Feuga under subtask 8.1.2, based on the initial plans stated in the Grant Agreement, and refined in terms of contents and structure with the support of WP leaders. The website information is organized following an intuitive structure, with 7 main sections: Homepage, MiniStor overall description, Our Work, Knowledge Centre, Links, News, and Contact. It is also linked to MiniStor's dedicated and social media channels.

The website was launched on M6, and throughout the project it accumulated 40 news and two dozen other items plus the public deliverables, with major technical updates in 2023 and 2025 that guarantee it will operate until 2030, far beyond what is expected in the Horizon 2020 research framework.

DIRECTORY

Latest MiniStor Newsletters

1st MiniStor Newsletter

Our first newsletter is now ready for you.

[Click here!](#)

May 2025 Newsletter

June 2025 Newsletter

BE THE FIRST ONE TO GET IT!

Would you like to receive our newsletter?

Subscribe to our newsletter and be the first one to receive the latest project developments! Fill in the form in the bottom below with the subject "newsletter".

[Contact Form](#)

Figure 1.

Figure 1 Excerpt from the MiniStor's website featuring the Newsletters.

Established as the main communication channel for MiniStor, the website performance was as dependent as social media on the actual public activity of the project. It was successful in engaging a broad audience and supporting the contents; however, in order to position itself by linking to other sites, and due to most materials being of a visual nature instead of technical documents (for those were either attached or in Zenodo), the average time spent by visit never grew past one minute and a half, even reducing slightly in the last year of the project. This may be explained by the fact that MiniStor reached a greater audience which bounced more frequently after checking just a couple of pages or accessing a document.

Overall, the result was positive, achieving a higher ceiling on monthly unique user visits than expected. For the figures on this, a communication KPI table is available further down in this chapter, with an annex containing the full analysis for the last year of the project based on secure protocol-based SSL logs for non-tampering guarantee.

1.2. Zenodo

Integrated in the EU Open Research Repository and the OpenAIRE index, the MiniStor Zenodo community stores indefinitely the scientific knowledge in an accessible way, in compliance with the principles of granting open access to publications and using public repositories. A guideline for the use of Zenodo was developed alongside Deliverable 8.1 after consulting the consortium, considering the costs and procedures for publication, and assigning the roles of curator (FEUGA), review coordination (IERC) and exploitation and IP review (R2M).

The repository operation is straightforward, based on ORCID account ID or direct registration using an email account. An automatic Creative Commons license generator is provided if necessary. When uploading a publication, participants filled in as part of MiniStor and OpenAIRE so that Zenodo could tag and index properly. With regards to the licensing options, the partners accepted the use of Creative Commons Attribution-No Derivatives CC-BY-ND, protecting the scientific publications from changes, while only requiring Attribution for promotional materials.

The Zenodo community [<https://zenodo.org/communities/ministor/>] accumulated to the date of this report 258 downloads and 243 full visualisations in the online reading platform. It will remain a dissemination tool and a mechanism for accountability.

1.3. Social media

The two social media channels chosen for MiniStor evolved steadily in parallel during the first half of the project but drifted considerably since. LinkedIn was chosen for its business-oriented professional networking tool; an important platform for discussions among experts in the area and various stakeholders in general. X, or Twitter back then, was seen as a rapid and professional communication tool, allowing for real-time interactions and very high potential outreach towards MiniStor's target audience, using hashtags and thematic threads.

Figure 2 Social media follower trends

Given the trend from 2023 onwards, X was monitored closely as it transforms it into a “everything app” in the words of its owner. Only during 2023, the platform lost more than half of its revenue compared to 2022, cut staff by 80% and severely altered community rules, resulting in a loss of safety, content moderation and user experience. Being a private company, X is not mandated to publicly share their traffic in the United States, but is legally obliged to disclose its user numbers in the EU.

Globally, X stated in 2025 that daily users had declined 10% to around 140 million people. Traffic suffered in all but two Member States, with the most dramatic cases in Spain, France and Poland (11 million users left in these three countries in 2024 alone), where MiniStor had consortium members.

Specialised media estimates that real, human users could be down to 80 million, or around 60% of what it was in 2022. Part of the users migrated to BlueSky, Mastodon and especially Threads, the only one to consistently outgrow the rest of the market of social media. This could explain why in the moment of maximum audience and contents, the follower count for MiniStor dropped from 504 to 486, instead of getting closer to the goal of 700.

For comparison, LinkedIn maintained a strong 310 million monthly users figure, 875 million users in total and more than 257 of them in Europe only; nevertheless, average time spent in LinkedIn is of only 17 minutes per month, which speaks of the specialisation of this network and must be accounted for. The KPI of more than 200 followers was accomplished with ease, totalling 248 users.

1.4. Videos

The planning regarding the promotional videos was influenced by two factors, the first being the reduced chances for in-person meetings after the pandemic outbreak in 2020, and the second the

calendar of unit delivery. Changes in the social media channels' algorithms also meant a slight pivot towards short videos that could boost visibility and performance.

After the first promotional video was uploaded in 2021, it was followed shortly after by the IoT and AR/VR demonstration videos, with a duration of 3 minutes 45 seconds and 2 minutes respectively. The former was also translated into French for Sofrigam to show in national fairs and later in CES Las Vegas.

Then, as the units were deployed in the demonstrations and became operational, a second row of videos was produced to showcase the prototype before the final conference, which was livestreamed and stored in the Youtube channel. Both had their own shorter version as well. That last push made MiniStor surpass the KPI of one thousand visualisations by June 2025.

Figure 3 Display of MiniStor and Sofrigam technologies aided by the first promotional video in CES Las Vegas 2024.

Figure 4 Snapshots of the videos published by MiniStor

The second promotional video was not simply an update of the first one; rather, they accompanied the overarching strategy by adhering to specific messages and audiences. Using stock imagery and animated infographics, the format 'What is MiniStor?' explored the MiniStor ecosystem by contextualising the funding call and the proposed solution, whereas 'MiniStor: Minimal Size Thermal and Electrical Energy Storage System' focused on the comparative advantages from the point of view of the end-user, with footage coming from the visits to the ÉMI testbed and the Santiago demonstrator.

1.5. Materials

Aside from the templates included in Deliverable 8.1 to aid the project partners and keep visual identity consistent, Work Package 8 developed a series of materials to be used in physical and online forms in support of MiniStor's public activity. This effort could be condensed in the three specific brochures developed in 2020, 2022 and 2025 to keep up with project demands and updates. In a similar fashion, the original rollout was updated to reflect the advancement of MiniStor's research.

Overall, 100 brochures and flyers were distributed alongside 200 copies of the EUSEW 2024 issue of the EU Energy Innovation magazine; more on this specific action is mentioned in the section Publications.

Figure 5 Excerpt from the 2022 brochure.

Figure 6 The 2025 version of the brochure tryptich, inside part.

Figure 7 MiniStor presence in the ECTP Conference 2021

Figure 8 MiniStor rollup in the Final Conference June 2025.

Figure 9 Supplementary materials for visual support in the EUSEW Energy Fair June 2025, including a reproduction of the prototype enclosure

Figure 10 Flyer linking to the policy briefs stored in the Zenodo community in June 2025.

Figure 11 Example of the visual identity in different MiniStor materials, a folder and a tryptich.

With regards to infographics, up to 14 specific designs were put at consortium disposal, covering demonstrator sites, technological drivers and the MiniStor ecosystem. These have made their way into rollups, brochures, social media posts and policy briefs, given the complex nature of the solution.

Figure 12 Infographics design line comparison from 2020 to 2025.

1.6. Newsletters

MiniStor newsletters are available on the website and were disseminated via social media and the partners' contribution. As agreed during the consultation previous to D8.1, no contact lists were created for the distribution of the newsletter to avoid any possible non-compliance with data protection; instead, they work as a stand-alone landing page that can be easily linked to any other channel.

As previously noted, the communication campaigns were more active until the pilots were ready. This impacted the Newsletter's release due to the connection of the different materials related to the demonstration sites. As a result, a renewed effort in 2025 put the total number of newsletters in 3, only down one from what was expected in the Grant Agreement.

Figure 13 Excerpt from the third newsletter, supported by Mailchimp.

1.7. Press releases and non-scientific publications

A total of 7 press releases were sent out by the end of the project. The quantity reflects the variety of organisations that made MiniStor, ranging from internationally positioned universities to SMEs. This was a particular challenge when reaching out to traditional media, for local channels were often too specific for what the WP8 could cover, even if partners agreed to a certain strategy during the first year of research. In the end, most of the beneficiaries opted for their national fairs and events that could attain several objectives of their own at the same time.

Therefore, the management of Communication had to rely on bigger occasions to get the attention of the press, or partnering with other initiatives: the launch of the project through partners' own channels and distributing an interview with the coordinator; the SB4EU and EeB PPP catalogues; the field visit to Santiago including another interview with national media; the Final Conference covered separately via the European Commission portal, BuildUp and Cluegal; and another two press releases via Euractiv, including paid coverage, during the final stage of the project.

Figure 14 EeB PPP Review excerpt.

Advanced materials and nanotechnology
Technology Building Blocks

MiniStor ^[61] Minimal Size Thermal and Electrical Energy Storage System for In-Situ Residential Installation

MiniStor will design and produce a compact integrated thermal storage system for achieving sustainable heating, cooling and electricity storage that can be adapted to existing systems in residential buildings. It is based on a high-performing thermochemical material reaction combined with parallel hot and cold phase-change materials for flexibility and usage year-round. It also stores electrical energy in a Lithium-ion battery that responds to grid signals and can sell to the electrical grid.

Start date: October 2019
Duration: 54 months
Status: Ongoing

Total budget: 8.53 M€
Website: ministor.eu
Coordinator: University College Cork - Tyndall National Institute, Ireland
Partners:
France: CNRS-PROMES
Greece: CERTH, DUTH
Hungary: EML, WOODSPRING
Ireland: IERC, Cork City Council
Italy: R2M Solution
Poland: Enetech Spolka Z Ograniczona Odpowiedzialnoscia
Spain: CARTIF, University of Santiago de Compostela, ENDEF, SGS
TECNOS SA, Fundación Empresa Universidad Gallega (FEUGA)
Switzerland: HSLU
United Kingdom: The University of Edinburgh (UEDIN)

Press releases require strong coordination and adequate information from and for the partners. To facilitate that, a new Media Kit was elaborated in 2024 to update the original guidelines from D8.1. Also featuring useful examples, using a media kit avoided duplication of efforts and provided a more targeted approach to the promotional activities.

One of these examples was the publication of a non-scientific article in the European Energy Innovation (EEI) review. It set the standard for the claims to be made with 2024 results available, the main points for the general public and a consensus, updated definition of MiniStor's concept.

MiniStor, the reliable thermal storage solution for all climates and households

Flexible, high-capacity heating and cooling technologies are ready to leverage the variability of renewable energy in the residential sector

Ministor, a Horizon 2020 project, is testing its high-density thermal storage system in multiple climate conditions and home configurations, providing both heating and cooling in an integrated yet flexible unit. The consortium, gathering seventeen partners from the EU and Switzerland, and

coordinated by ERC, has reached its final phase with the deployment of units across 5 demonstration sites. Operating year-round, Ministor aims to provide energy security across Europe's residential sector with a thermal storage density well over 10 times that of water, a practical solution for leveraging the variability of renewable energy sources.

Concept
At its core, the system combines an efficient thermochemical storage and a phase-change material that stores latent heat. When paired, the multi-day energy storage reactor based on CaCl₂/NH₃ salts along with the PCM storages for cooling and heating reach a high density of 213 kWh/m³, allowing a minimal size installation and scalability. This state-of-the-art thermal storage setting is ready to be deployed.

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At a suitable distance from the Ministor container, there are also unique solar hybrid photovoltaic thermal (PVT) collectors, which not only reach the required heat for activating the reactor, but also generate electricity for a battery system. ENDEF's newly design PVT panels include glazed collectors, with a laminate of 200Wp, to be combined with solar thermal flat plate collectors (FPC), and unglazed collectors, with a laminate of 300Wp.

Critically, the entire operation is handled via the Home Energy Management System (HEMS), a smart digital tool developed by CERTH. Key to the technology fusion, it is now being developed into a second iteration to actively consider demand and generation predictors to help in carbon control and long-term decision-making. Alongside an Internet of Things (IoT) platform build by CERTH, it will help in the user-

centric approach and allow obtaining feedback from users. In conjunction, the Ministor system leverages the variability of renewable energy sources, saving thermal and electrical energy until they are in short supply.

Demonstration
One of the prototypes was at a test environment from April to May, under operation modes at the EM facilities. The analysis of said evaluations is nearly finished, but it already served SGS in the preparation of Ministor's own Project Audit Program, covering the manufacturing process in Pycnotherm as well.

The main evaluations build on the Thessaloniki pre-pilot at CERTH premises, where Ministor was first installed in December 2023. During the preliminary tests, commissioning and optimisation of the system control, performance and safety measures were accounted for and evaluated through certification of the

Ministor has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869821

Figure 15 Excerpt of the EEI Review issue of summer 2024 distributed in the EUSEW conference.

The quarterly publication was distributed physically in collaboration with the EUSEW in a quantity of two hundred copies, aside from particular or pre-existing agreements with associated entities, industry and institutions. The EUSEW is the main forum for sector representatives and policymakers, entrepreneurs and members of the civil society discussing EU's long-term competitiveness, resilience and efficiency through net-zero energy solutions such as MiniStor.

After three decades, the EEI has reached 10.000 subscribers; the review is also delivered to the Members of the European Parliament, around four hundred peers from several committees, as well as European ministries and senior members of the Commission, from Directors General to Heads of unit in Energy, Environment, Research and Innovation or Climate Action, among others, for a total audience over 30.000 stakeholders.

This action was duly complemented the year after using both the press release and native services from Euractiv, the EU affairs specialised media network bridging 11 European capitals, with 162.000 followers and 1 million visits per month, while also addressing directly policymakers in the field of Energy with curated contents.

Figure 16 Euractiv OpEd on the Final Conference

The total accumulated publications in sector-specific magazines, nevertheless, fell short of the objective, with 29 articles reported by the consortium. This is a reflection, as indicated before, of the diversity of profiles and possible contributions, but also of the difficulties of a long-term Research and Innovation Action from the H2020 framework to publish before the final results are available in a project of such complexity, where multiple technologies fusion into one ecosystem that has no direct comparison in the market available solutions.

Some of the press releases were "picked up" by newspapers having national reach in the consortium countries of MiniStor, which allowed the project to be known by the general public. As for media appearances, the project made it 15 times to general press, including 2 interviews with the project coordinator in Irish and Spanish outlets. These two examples include an article published in La Voz de Galicia on 9 June 2025 (highest ranking newspaper in Galicia region and 8th in Spain), and The Irish Examiner on 25 April 2025 (most read newspaper in Munster province and distributed nationwide). The usefulness of the system was contrasted with national events related to energy, such as the national blackout in Spain, or the rise of energy bills in Ireland. The articles appeared both in print and online. The project featured in 2 pieces for Greek public TV channel EPT1 on phase-change materials plus the Kimmeria demonstrator and the Heron educational visits programme for students.

Figure 17 Screenshots of articles published in print and online, and screenshots of TV piece describing the MiniStor system

The total accumulated publications in sector-specific magazines, nevertheless, fell short of the objective, with 29 articles reported by the consortium. This is a reflection, as indicated before, of the diversity of profiles and possible contributions, but also of the difficulties of a long-term Research and Innovation Action from the H2020 framework to publish before the final results are

available in a project of such complexity, where multiple technologies fusion into one ecosystem that has no direct comparison in the market available solutions.

The table below offers a detailed account of the Key Performance Indicators for communication activities as set in the Grant Agreement.

Table 1 Communication KPIs.

Channel activity	Key performance indicators (KPI)	Common objectives	Achieved
MiniStor website (SSL domain)	N° of visitors	1000 visitors /month in the last year of the project	3742
	Time of visit	with +2 min average staying	1 min 28 sec
	N° of news	> 50	40
MiniStor Social Media	N° of followers (X/Twitter)	> 700	486 followers
	N° of followers (LinkedIn)	>200	248 followers
Youtube	N° of views	>1000	1004 total
Press releases	N° of press releases	2 per project partner	7
Partners' existing communication channels	N° of audience members reached	To reach a combined audience over 40,000 people (all partners)	178.750 from partners only, 375.550 including networks
Leaflet	N° of Leaflets distributed	50000	300
Newsletters	N° of newsletters	yearly	3
Videos	N° of promotional videos	2	4

1.8. Policy Briefs

Acting on the recommendations from the first and second Review Meetings, three Policy Briefs were produced to support the dissemination efforts by the time of the Final Conference. Three previously arranged task forces, comprised of seven partners, began preparations and delivered the first outputs by Month 61. Then, the work was completed following a bi-monthly calendar of meetings and a 6-step process to gradually fill a template in.

The task forces worked separately, although with the support of R2M for the initial assessment and final review, in preparing a two-pager on thermal storage technologies, another two-pager on PVT development, and a longer document with recommendations to modernise the legislative framework for ammonia usage in the residential sector.

Figure 18 Promotional image for the distribution of the policy briefs.

After the review of the consortium partners, the three policy briefs were made available in Zenodo [https://zenodo.org/communities/ministor/] and the website, being distributed during the Final Conference using a A5 flyer format and in social media. The presentation of these documents was the cornerstone of the policy session, setting the stage for the expert round table. More on this on the section dedicated to the closing event.

Figure 19 Display of the three policy briefs first page

1.9. Scientific publications

Publications in journals and conferences are a conventional and effective way to disseminate project outcomes and attract the attention of scientific, business and public stakeholders. MiniStor's initial

target included 10 publications in international journals and papers presented in scientific conferences and workshops.

Scientific dissemination was mainly the responsibility of research partners. However, to support this effort, publications are also featured in the official website and in the Zenodo community when the conditions of access made it possible. In order to account for publications, as well as other dissemination actions, a Tracker was created in Month 6 so that the partners were able to fill a Google Drive table in each time they submitted a publication or attended an event.

Table 2 List of peer-reviewed publications

Partner(s)	Title	Type	Planned date	Published/ Location
CERTH, CNRS, ENDEF	Conceptual design and dynamic simulation of an integrated solar driven thermal system with thermochemical energy storage for heating and cooling	Green Open Access	21.01.2021	Journal of Energy Storage
DUTH	Thermal/Cooling Energy on Local Energy Communities: A critical review	Gold Open Access	02.02.2022	Energies, MDPI
ENDEF	Energy Performance of Four Prototypes of PVT Collectors. A Comparative Study.	Green Open Access	10.07.2022	EuroSun 2022 proceeding
CARTIF	Programación de controlador para sistema de generación y almacenamiento térmico en edificio	Green Open Access	2022	Universidad de Valladolid
CERTH	Power Load Forecasting: A Time-Series Multi-Step Ahead and Multi-Model Analysis	Green Open Access	30.08.2023	UPEC Conference
CERTH	Optimizing the performance of a novel compact integrated thermal storage system (MiniStor) under diverse climate conditions	Green Open Access	31.05.2025	Green Energy and Sustainability (ICRES Special Issue)

1.10. Clustering and networking

WP8 successfully established contacts with relevant projects identified in the stakeholder database, particularly those originating from similar calls focused on thermal and electric energy storage. Through these interactions, common challenges were identified, and coordinated actions were proposed to address them under a mutual strategy developed collaboratively by SGS and EMI.

Here is a summary of the relevant links established, which comfortably surpassed the goal of 10 joint initiatives. Other considered links were EUREC, Bioenergy Europe, EGEC, Euroheat and EHPA.

- Certification: project D2EPC (2022)
- Normalisation and standardisation: UNE, CTN-100, CTN-113 (2024)
- Construction: ECTP, EeB PPP, SB4EU (including Smart Readiness Indicator via R2M) (2021); BUILD UP (2022); project Probono (2023)

- Storage: SunHorizon (2021), Hystore, Agriculture Victoria (2023)
- Renewable Heating and Cooling: RHC-ETIP working groups and four editions of Sustainable Places (2020), SteamDry, ProdutechR3 (2025)
- Clustering: ENLIT, POwR Earth Foundation (2024), Cluergal, Solar Heat Europe (2025)

This effort run in conjunction with Task 8.3, where SGS addressed the standardisation and professional bodies to address challenges related to certification, safety, and regulatory alignment. Monthly coordination meetings with FEUGA ensured consistent progress, while collaborative work with EMI supported the development of Deliverable 8.5 and the validated opinion as successor of the Product Audit Program. A structured action plan was implemented, including screening existing standards, exploring contributions to new ones via CEN-CENELEC Workshop Agreements, and engaging with national standardization bodies such as UNE (Spain).

Later on, this led to targeted participation in relevant technical standardisation committees, notably CTN-100 and CEN/TC 113, culminating in a formal presentation of MiniStor's system and achievements to the CTN-100 Plenary. The presentation highlighted system components, certification processes, and installation ease, while also identifying gaps in existing standards for thermal energy storage. Feedback from committee members underscored the need for cross-sectoral standard development.

1.11. Events and total audience by type

MiniStor's partners participated in a total of 27 international events and 8 national conferences and fairs, an imbalance that speaks of the increasing importance of EU-level events, clustering activities and, of course, of the increasing internationalisation of the consortium partners, that reached the United States, Colombia and Vietnam. They also contributed to 13 demonstration and dissemination workshops addressed at stakeholders, in line with expectations.

In terms of the public reached, these events gathered 90.945 industry and value chain representatives, 23.950 potential customers, 11.950 investors, 7.150 researchers, 459 policy makers, 29 media outlets, 169 members of the civil society, and 1.065 students. On top of that, 178.750 people from the general public were reached through online channels of the partners; if we include all the events, networks and press work, calculated on the aggregated low-end to minimise duplication, a grand total 494.150 individuals came in contact with MiniStor since 2019.

Table 3 List of covered events

Event	Date	Partners	Location	Dissemination Level
Sustainable Places 2020	29/10/2020	FEUGA, IREC, R2M, CARTIF, CERTH, ENDEF	Virtual workshop	European
SSTES 2020	24/01/2020	HSLU	Lucerne, Switzerland	International
Sustainable Places 2021	30/09/2021	IREC, R2M, DUTH	Virtual workshop	European
IEA – SHC	02/10/2020	ENDEF	Virtual workshop	European

Galicia Innovation Days	26/10/2021	FEUSGA, IREC, DUTH, CARTIF, WOODSPRING	Virtual workshop (mid-term dissemination)	European
ECTP 2021 Conference	02-03/12/2021	FEUGA	Madrid, Spain	European
Genera 2021	16-18/11/2021	ENDEF	Madrid, Spain	EU Trade fair
Planet Budapest 2021	03/12/2021	EMI	Budapest, Hungary	International
Construma 2022	06/04/2022	EMI	Budapest, Hungary	International
SEAI Energy Show 2022	30/03/2022	IREC	Dublin, Ireland	National
EUROSUN 2022	25-29/09/2022	ENDEF	Kassel, Germany	International
D^2EPC	08/06/2022	SGS, IREC	Virtual	European
Sustainable Places 2022	30/09/2021	IREC, R2M, DUTH	Virtual workshop	European
EUSEW 2022	06/09/2022	R2M, ENDEF, CERTH, DUTH, CNRS	Nice, France	European
BUILDUP Webinar	26/01/2023	IREC, CERTH	Virtual	European
ECCA 2023	19-21/06/2023	IREC, FEUGA	Dublin, Ireland	European
ECPT 2023 Assembly	07/06/2023	FEUGA	Barcelona, Spain	European
Sustainable Places 2023	14-16/06/2023	R2M	Madrid, Spain	International
Construma 2023	29/03/2023	EMI	Budapest, Hungary	International
Pollack Expo 2023	13-14/04/2023	EMI	Pècs, Hungary	National
III International Seminar on Sustainable Engineering	25/11/2023	ENDEF	Barranquilla, Colombia	International
CES 2024	09-12/01/2024	Sofrigam	Las Vegas, US	International
International Symposium on Applied Science 2023	13-15/10/2023	Woodspring	Ho Chi Min City, Vietnam	International
PowR Earth Summit	13-15/03/2023	Sofrigam	Paris, France	International

Eurosun 2024	26-30/08/2024	ENDEF, CARTIF, CERTH	Limassol, Chipre	International
ENLIT 2024	23/10/2024	R2M	Milan, Italy	International
AEPIBAL Day. III National Energy Storage Meeting	28/11/2024	ENDEF	Zaragoza, Spain	National
ECTP 2024	05/03/2024	FEUGA, ÉMI, CARTIF	Brussels, Belgium	International
Pôle Cristal 2024	05/11/2024	Sofrigam	Dinan, France	National
ICRES 2025	11/04/2025	CERTH	Thessaloniki, Greece	International
IEA - Solar Heating and Cooling (SHC) Program, Task 73	13/02/2025	ENDEF	Berlin, Germany	International
MiniStor Final Conference	09/06/2025	All	Brussels, Belgium	International
Congreso CAE	25/06/2025	SGS	Madrid, Spain	National
Jornada CAE	20/06/2025	SGS	Castellón, Spain	National

1.12. Final Conference Summary

For the final dissemination phase, WP8 updated the different materials produced to accommodate the results of the project. The approach prioritised stakeholders and end-users in a more individualised and targeted manner to reach the dissemination objectives and ensure MiniStor results are assimilated and have an impact beyond the project lifetime. In parallel, the Final Conference was to pursue stronger involvement of policymakers and market actors, complementing the mid-term international event organised during the pandemic lockdowns.

As stated in the Grant Agreement, the Final Conference was supposed to prioritise a framework event at EU level in Brussels (e.g. Sustainable Energy Week, EU Regions Week, ECTP Conference, etc.) to ensure wider participation and impact. General results and project demonstration cases would be showcased during the Conference alongside the policy set.

The EU Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW) was chosen due to the proximity to the end of the project and the fact that the ECTP Conference was a biannual occasion. By January 2025, MiniStor had presented a policy session proposal for June 11th, but lacking endorsement from a youth, consumer or industry association, it was registered separately and merged with the result session of the project, an Energy Day under the umbrella of the EUSEW from June 10 to 11. To complement this, a Energy Fair stand was secured alongside projects Steamdry and Maxima, under the denomination Powering a Green Europe: EU Projects in Action, in stand C-5. The Energy Fair runned for the bulk of the EUSEW, showcasing innovative projects and technologies in sustainable energy and energy efficiency.

Figure 20 Part of the MiniStor delegation in the Energy Fair as part of EUSEW 2025.

As part of the European Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW), Europe's flagship annual event dedicated to renewable energy and energy efficiency, the MiniStor project held its final conference in Brussels on June 9-10, marking a key milestone in the project's journey. The event, titled "Reaching the Decarbonisation Goal", celebrated the project's conclusion by presenting its most impactful research findings, technological innovations, and policy recommendations.

Both programmes were made compatible for convenience of the attendees. Research results as well as policy recommendations were presented in the De Gasperi theatre room of the NH Brussels Berlaymont, whereas the Energy Fair was held in the Charlemagne building, at 5-minute distance by walk.

Hosted in a hybrid format, the conference welcomed both in-person attendees and a wider online audience via livestream on the MiniStor YouTube channel. Participation was significant, with the engagement of 26 Institutions. Regarding attendance, 38 people registered in-person, of which 31 joined us in the venue, including members from MiniStor's Consulting and Ethical Boards (Cardiff University, University of Warwick); academia (University of Barcelona, ISQ, INESC TEC, WUR, UCD); and industry associations (CLUERGAL, Solar Heat Europe). Including project partners, 11 countries were represented. Another 97 people followed the event online.

Figure 21 Policy session round table, final conference.

The event was structured around two core sessions:

- June 9 – Presentation of Project Results
- June 10 – Policy Session

The conference opened with remarks from Óscar Bernárdez, EU Projects Manager at FEUGA, responsible for MiniStor dissemination and communication. He introduced the consortium partners and outlined the conference objectives. Following the introduction, Dr Carlos Ochoa, Senior Researcher at IERC and MiniStor Project Coordinator, presented the project's purpose, objectives, and key outcomes.

A highlight of the conference was the presentation by Prof Driss Stitou, Scientific Director at CNRS, who introduced the project's core technological innovation: the TCM system. This system leverages the reaction between calcium chloride and ammonia salts, combined with parallel hot and cold PCMs. Compared to conventional thermal storage solutions, the TCM technology demonstrated a thermal storage density 10 times greater than water, positioning MiniStor as a groundbreaking solution for managing the variability of renewable energy sources.

Figure 22 MiniStor TCM system presentation during the Final Conference

Dr Georgios Martinopoulos, research associate at CERTH-CPERI, presented the testing and demonstration activities. MiniStor was evaluated across five sites tailored to different European climate zones: two in Mediterranean climates, two influenced by Atlantic Ocean conditions, and one in a continental-humid environment. Results showed highly promising performance, achieving an interesting efficiency and reducing residential thermal energy consumption.

Marco Rocchetti, Head of Energy & Technology at R2M Solution, discussed the market potential and scalability of the MiniStor solution. The financial analysis demonstrated that MiniStor is not only economically viable but also highly scalable, with strong potential for commercial uptake, especially in the residential sector.

To close the conference, Dr Yolanda Lara, R&D Manager at EndeF Engineering, presented the project's policy brief alongside Carlos Ochoa. The session highlighted key performance indicators related to MiniStor environmental and economic impact, with the goal of incentivising the adoption TES in buildings. The brief also aimed to engage potential investors and regulators to support the solution's path to market.

The event also featured presentations from sister projects such as HYSTORE, STEAMDRY, and PRODUTECH R3, which shared their objectives and collaborative achievements. These exchanges opened new opportunities for synergies and future cooperation across the sustainable energy landscape; for instance, Sofrigam is now an Associate Member of Solar Heat Europe in the category of the solar value chain.

Figure 23 Final Conference networking area.

The 2025 edition of EU Sustainable Energy Week under the title 'Powering a fair and competitive green transition' took place from 10 to 12 June in Brussels and online. MiniStor, alongside projects Maxima and SteamDry, hosted Stand C-5, in the second floor of the Charlemagne Building, during the Energy Fair, which showcased innovative projects and technologies in sustainable energy and energy efficiency.

Since its launch in 2007 by the European Commission, EUSEW has grown into a key platform for dialogue and collaboration on EU energy policies and initiatives. It is an annual flagship conference by the Directorate-General for Energy (DG ENER) co-organised with the European Climate, Infrastructure, and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). This edition had over 2.000 in-person attendees.

Table 4 Dissemination KPIs

Channel / activity	Key performance indicators (KPI)	Common objectives	Achieved
Stakeholders workshop, & mid-term National workshops	N° of attendees	50 per workshop 400 stakeholders approx. attending project's events	896 (including online and in-person workshops), average 112
Final Conference	N° of attendees	100 Final conference	164
Demonstration workshops / dissemination	N° of workshops + 1 link EC Policy*	6 / 50 stakeholders each	13 / 1154 *EUSEW

Participation in events	N° of international events	At least 2 per partner after 2nd year	27
	N° of national conference	2 per partner	8
Infographics	Per pilot site	5	14
Publications	N° of publications in sector-specific magazines	1 publication/year per partner	29
Scientific Articles	N° of published articles	More than 10 articles	6
Clustering with other projects/entities	N° of Joint actions	At least 10 joint actions	19
Policy Briefs	N° of policy briefs	3	3

Table 5 Number and types of persons reached per sector

Sector	Number	Calculation
Research	7.150	Tracker, clustering participants and networks members
Industry	90.945	Tracker
Civil society	169	Associations members
General public	178.750	Aggregate low-end total audience in social media of partners, not individuals, that shared at least one news or article regarding the project, without duplicating followers in social media channels; including events and networks 494.150
Policy makers	459	Final Conference, EEI physical distribution, Tracker
Media	29	Media outlets engaged with impacts after events or newsletters
Investors	11.950	Tracker
Customers	23.950	Tracker (Fairs)
Other	1065	DUTH MTEEP educational guided tours programme; 250 monthly average visitors

Table 6 Total Audiences table per partner and per initiative (includes all channels)

Partner	Audiences reached (all channels)
CNRS	2.000
FEUGA	21.000
IERC / TYNDALL	24.800

R2M	8.000
ENDEF	1.800
SOFRIGAM	3.000
HSLU	3.000
USC	115.000
EMI	630
PSY	1.300
Initiative	Audiences reached (all channels)
RHC	800 members
ECTP	1000 / 150 organisations
EUSEW	23.000
EEI	10.000
EURACTIV	162.000
BUILDUP	4.300
HYSTORE (DCU)	1.460
SOLAR HEAT EUROPE	4.000 / 44 members
CLUERGAL	8.100 / 125 members
EVENTS TOTAL	118.600

Conclusion

The MiniStor project's final communication and dissemination report, Deliverable D8.2, offers a comprehensive reflection on the strategic efforts undertaken throughout the project's lifecycle. One of the key learning points is the importance of flexibility and adaptability in long-term research initiatives. The original communication strategy, outlined in Deliverable D8.1, was designed as a living document, allowing for updates and realignments. Recalibration of priorities was done according to project developments, with Work Package 8 focusing towards dissemination and networking, while maintaining overall goals regarding reaching the general public.

Another major insight is the value of coordinated clustering actions. MiniStor's dissemination efforts were structured around five strategic phases, targeting awareness, results sharing, and policy influence. The project successfully engaged a wide range of end-users and stakeholders—including policymakers, industry representatives, researchers, and potential customers—through events, publications, and digital channels.

The Final Conference, held during EU Sustainable Energy Week 2025, exemplified this approach by combining research presentations with policy discussions, thereby maximizing visibility and impact. The production of three policy briefs addressing thermal storage, PVT development, and ammonia

usage in residential settings further reinforced MiniStor's commitment to influencing regulatory frameworks.

The document also highlights the critical role of digital tools and branding in sustaining project visibility. The MiniStor website served as the central hub for communication, complemented by social media channels (LinkedIn and X/Twitter), newsletters, press releases, and promotional videos. Despite challenges with platform changes—particularly the decline in X/Twitter's effectiveness—LinkedIn proved to be a reliable channel for professional engagement. The use of Zenodo for open-access publication ensured long-term accessibility of scientific outputs, aligning with EU transparency and data-sharing principles.

From a performance standpoint, MiniStor met or exceeded most of its Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), including website traffic, video views, and stakeholder outreach. However, some targets—such as social media followers and scientific publications—fell slightly short due to the project's complexity and timeline constraints. Nevertheless, MiniStor's reach was considerable, with nearly half a million individuals coming into contact with the project in the 68 months covered by the grant.

In conclusion, Deliverable D8.2 underscores the importance of strategic planning, network alignment, and adaptive execution in achieving effective communication and dissemination in the Horizon 2020 framework. WP8 demonstrated resolve and proactivity in navigating disruptions, leveraging partnerships, and delivering impactful materials. The project's legacy is not only in its technological advancements but also in its contribution to policy dialogue and public awareness around sustainable thermal energy storage. These lessons offer valuable guidance for future initiatives aiming to bridge research and practice to reach a high Technological Readiness Level.

Annex I. Web report for the last year of the project.

Report for MiniStor RP5 2	
Time range: 01/07/2024 00:02:52 - 30/06/2025 02:03:48	Generated on Fri Aug 01, 2025 - 10:46:12
General Statistics	
Summary	
Summary	
Hits	
Total Hits	827,081
Visitor Hits	688,908
Spider Hits	138,173
Average Hits per Day	2,265
Average Hits per Visitor	5.03
Cached Requests	4,128
Failed Requests	142,660
Page Views	
Total Page Views	337,224
Average Page Views per Day	923
Average Page Views per Visitor	2.46
Visitors	
Total Visitors	137,096
Average Visitors per Day	375
Total Unique IPs	44,915
Bandwidth	
Total Bandwidth	22.67 GB
Visitor Bandwidth	17.41 GB
Spider Bandwidth	5.27 GB
Average Bandwidth per Day	63.61 MB
Average Bandwidth per Hit	28.75 KB
Average Bandwidth per Visitor	133.13 KB

Activity Statistics

Daily

Daily Visitors

Daily Hits

By Day of Week

Activity by Day of Week

Activity by Day of Week

Day	Hits	Page Views	Visitors	Bandwidth (KB)
Sunday	89,865	40,958	17,592	2,151,445
Monday	130,048	47,526	18,409	3,954,790
Tuesday	130,725	55,777	19,778	3,420,250
Wednesday	138,366	57,957	21,331	5,075,206
Thursday	118,614	47,509	21,466	3,442,506
Friday	126,006	45,641	20,105	3,286,265
Saturday	93,457	41,856	18,415	2,445,156
Total	827,081	337,224	137,096	23,775,621

By Month

Activity by Month

Month	Hits	Page Views	Visitors	Bandwidth (KB)
Jul 2024	48,755	13,311	7,725	1,305,835
Aug 2024	48,843	12,656	7,889	1,231,848
Sep 2024	51,090	17,691	11,982	1,216,074
Oct 2024	60,690	22,318	14,162	1,298,140

7

Nov 2024	65,492	23,393	13,666	1,193,221
Dec 2024	61,518	28,509	13,803	2,003,331
Jan 2025	66,337	30,560	12,670	1,810,942
Feb 2025	59,501	29,276	10,109	1,891,013
Mar 2025	64,751	29,222	10,001	1,727,983
Apr 2025	78,591	28,726	11,478	1,946,106
May 2025	92,474	39,840	11,696	3,490,511
Jun 2025	129,039	61,722	11,915	4,660,611
Total	827,081	337,224	137,096	23,775,621

Device Types

Device Types

